

A Peer Reviewed International Journal of Asian
Academic Research Associates

AARJMD

**ASIAN ACADEMIC RESEARCH
JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY**

**HEURIST CUM STATISTICAL APPROACH FOR CITY
CLEANLINESS RATING SYSTEM**

**RUDRANARAYAN MOHAPATRA*, PINAK RANADE*, YOGESH SINGH*,
NITIN PAWAR*, VIVEK KADALWAR*, NAMRATA AILAWAR*,
HEMANT KHOGTA*, SAJISH C.*, SANTOSH KUMAR*,
MOHAMMAD AZIZ MAALIK *,
NEHA GUPTA*, VAIBHAV POL*, GAURAV MISHRA***

*Centre for Development of Advanced Computing (C-DAC), Under Ministry of IT &
Communications, Government of India, Pune University Campus, Pune – 411007 India

Abstract

Urban population is increasing rapidly for many reasons including fast increase in the country's total population, more job opportunities, better living standards, and availability of reliable utility services in the cities. This trend is predicted to continue for decades to come, therefore, managing cities on a sustainable way is a challenge that receives increasing attention from policy-makers and researchers. Cleanliness Rating System is an effective and systematic process to measure and maintain cleanliness within the society by means of recognized rating mechanism giving citizens an active role. In order to achieve this, the proposed system is going to cater an innovative approach to clean our environment in a participatory manner giving citizens an active role. The system, a state-of-the-art solution, adopts a more subjective approach by using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to assess the cleanliness activities for Sustainable Urban Clean Healthy India Transformation through Rating (SUCHITRa). The objective is to define a set of standards that can be used to measure the cleanliness of public areas.

Keywords – *Cleanliness, Rating system, Cloud, Analytic Hierarchy process (AHP)*

Introduction

If the place isn't clean, it is unlikely to impress anyone. The same applies to an entire world as the lack of basic cleanliness in public places at present is glaring, and also a paramount concern to developing countries like India. Therefore, Mahatma Gandhiji's mantra "Cleanliness is Godliness" urged the entire country's individual and community cleanliness for a healthy life and spirit. However, there are hardly any system and effective algorithm in the country to overcome this barrier that can be put to enforce and strengthen the cleanliness measurement activity.

In view of this, a rating mechanism using AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) is conceptualized to empower citizens to rate the cleanliness at public places to achieve their cleanliness right and make aware the responsible local authorities of places requiring immediate attention for cleaning. AHP is a process designed as structured technique to organized and analyzed complex decisions and has been extensively studied and refined up until now. The main objective of the proposed system is maintaining the cleanliness within the city by the means of rating mechanism.

Background

Historically, it is observed that a number of initiations are being carried out by different organizations throughout the world, in their respective mechanism to achieve the smart goal of cleanliness.

Department of the Environment, Heritage and Local Government and TOBIN Consulting Engineers comprising "*National Litter Pollution Monitoring System*" accepted five scale a litter pollution index to enable local authorities to manage litter pollution in a systematic, structured manner and resulted the percentage of unpolluted (LPI 1) areas increased from 10.4% to 2012 to 12.2% in 2013. The Cleanliness Index Monitoring System (CIMS) has been developed by Keep Scotland Beautiful (KSB) to assist local authorities to assess local environmental quality. Ministry of Tourism, Government of India has initiated for "*Study on development of Cleanliness Index for Cities*" in November 2013, with an aim to establish an index and undertake assessment of 15-20 Cities. The Central Pollution Control Board on its "Ecocity" project under X Plan works

in specific objectives to identify the environmental problems/hotspots in the identified towns and priority environmental improvement projects through participatory approach.

However, to achieve the desired cleanliness, some fill-gap factors for its sound performance are required. As of now, there are no standard prioritization cleanliness indexing activity is available with respect to location & time, no system providing information on how user's in-time cleanliness-rating activity affects their socio-economic backgrounds. On lines of this, a system has been conceptualized called 'SUCHITRa (System for Urban, Clean, Healthy India Transformation through Rating)'.

Proposed system

The system is conceptualized to empower citizens to rate the cleanliness at public places, make aware the responsible local authorities of places requiring immediate attention for cleaning. The proposed system SUCHITRa is a multi-purpose, multi-modal and multi-platform system having salient features like 'constant Surveillance to auditing, geo-tagging to localizing as well as feedback mechanism' to strengthen both citizens as well as to administrators' in hand-in-hand basis for cleanliness activities in a responsible and responsive manner.

The system will be implemented in both versions - standalone as well as Mobile application / internet version in order to feed both server as well as client side. The system would be put in place to evaluate and control the quality of cleaning services via online application tool / crowd sourcing which in turn allows the local-authorities, responsible for the service to evaluate the status of the cleaning of their cities in real time.

Implementation

The cleanliness problems will be monitored using Multi Criteria modeling which will classify the area into various zones, viz., ideal, very clean, clean, moderate, low clean, dirty and very dirty zones. An Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP) will be followed for calculating weights and ranking (from the data obtained from the feedback form), where Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP) will determine the relative importance of each criteria. Calculations will be carried out using computational rules and decisions will be made by comparing all the criteria pair-wise.

AHP is being used to analyze the data from the questionnaires. The indicators were compared to each other to obtain their priorities. The perk of using AHP is to allow the respondents to focus judgment separately on each of several properties essential for making a sound decision. Hence, the most effective way to obtain solid judgment is by pairing elements and compares them with single property without taking other properties into consideration. Normalization used in AHP contains information on the total dominance of the alternatives being compared to enable the allocation of the criterion priority to each alternative according to the relative dominance of the alternatives.

When determining the cleanliness-index and a process to assess the cleanliness of public areas, five factors are been considered such as: Rating Parameter, Assessment Areas, Assessment Frequencies, Number Assessors and Reporting. While, the 'Rating parameter' refers to standard and numerical rating scale used to measure the cleanliness of the public area, the assessment frequencies determines the locality required to be assessed for cleaning. Assessment Frequencies defines the number of times an area must be assessed and the Number Assessors denotes to number of individual participation in the rating activity. 'Reporting' depicts how the assessment data will be reported to the departments and public.

The proposed system SUCHITRa will work in an overall coordination between three main modules such as 'Data Filtration Module (DFM)', Central Rating Manager (C-RM) and Corporation Response Module (CRM). The data layer as an access to external systems mainly incorporates the elastic "cloud". Data access components isolate the service layer from the details of the specific data storage solution benefiting to minimize the impact of a change in database provider and by Minimizing the impact of a change in data representation as well as greatly simplifies testing and maintenance. The data collected through Data Filtration Module (DFM) will be categorically classified as text and images. The text data is further supplied to 'Zonal Rating Calculator (ZRC)' for its systematic rating calculation through Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP) with vis-vis-to Time-Action standard parameter, till the end of affirmative Sub-Zone N decision support. The ratio scales are derived from the principal Eigen vectors and the consistency index is derived from the principal Eigen value.

Where, Consistency Ratio (CR) is equal to the division of Consistency Index (CI) to

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (0.1)$$

Random Consistency Index (RI). i.e

$$\overline{CR} = \frac{\sum_i w_i CI_i}{\sum_i w_i RI_i} \quad (0.2)$$

And overall consistency

(Weighted consistency index CI is divided with weighted random consistency index (RI))

Further the data collected from Image Data Manager (IDM) by Central Rating Manager (C-RM) and the report generated by Zonal Rating Calculator (ZRC) will be further collectively forwarded to Corporate Response Module for its future course work. The Central Rating Manager (C-RM) will take hand-in-hand cleanliness activity using an in-between co-ordination of Resource Manager, Cleanliness Inspector and Report update Module for its cyclic process through Data Filtration Module (DFM) till the desired cleanliness action performed. A systematic architectural representation represented below (**Fig. 1**):

Fig. I

Constraints

The guiding principle is, "if cleanliness can be measured, then cleanliness can be managed". Based on GIS and Cloud technology, the SUCHITRa System will be subject to constant auditing and continual improvement. However, looking to the prior experience and Indian environment mobilizing both citizens, local authorities, NGO's, civic bodies and all involved stakeholders to participate in the rating process and extend their hand for Cleanliness program is always a challenge.

Further the different areas would have different categorization of cleanliness problem. Such as the area X may have higher levels of pedestrian litter than the average, Area Y may have higher levels of stray dog fouling and Area Z may have higher levels of business, domestic and construction. So categorizing and prioritizing the activity with coordination to local authority and fixing the higher rank would be a research constraint.

Conclusion

Many factors can increase the impact of cleanliness and the only way to achieve and maintain the appropriate cleanliness level, is to implement a comprehensive filtration program. The proposed

system SUCHITRa offers all the components that are needed to monitor and manage cleanliness across the area (Public places, rivers, lakes etc.).

The use of multi criteria analysis with heuristic cum statistical approach (by determining weight factor through pair wise comparison) is used for more effective and systematic cleanliness rating system. AHP used in the system for obtaining the ranks allows some small inconsistency in judgment because human is not always consistent.

In order to realize the maximum returns from the SUCHITRa rating system, all citizens need to be involved and be made stakeholders, which will make the citizen's life healthy and hygienic. The system, if implemented, will act as base to make the countries cleaner and in future, the same may be adopted by other developing countries as well.

References

1. Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) 'Ecocity' project, <http://cpcb.nic.in/Highlights/2006/ECO-ITYPROGRAMME%5B1%5D.pdf>
2. 'DC Clean City Assessment Ratings', Office of the Clean City Executive Office of the Mayor, Government of the District of Columbia, <http://fergusonfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/KeithPres.pdf>
3. <http://www.thehindu.com/news/national/cleanliness-index-soon-to-rank-cities/article6427602.ece> dated Sep 20, 2014
4. Keep Scotland Beautiful (KSB)'s "Cleanliness Index Monitoring System (CIMS), <http://www.livingstreets.org.uk/sites/default/files/content/library/toolkits/creatinghealthynvironments/3.3%20Cleanliness%20Index%20Monitoring%20%20System.pdf>
5. New rating system for restaurant cleanliness: does it protect the public?, <http://www.post-gazette.com/business/businessnews/2011/01/09/New-rating-system-for-restaurant-cleanliness-does-it-protect-the-public/stories/201101090186>
6. Ministry of Tourism, Government of India Request for Proposal (RFP) "Study on development of Cleanliness Index for Cities", <http://www.tourism.gov.in/writereaddata/Uploaded/Tender/101020131223846.pdf>
7. TOBIN Consulting Engineer, Thailand, "National Litter Pollution Monitoring System", <http://www.viron.ie/en/Publications/Environment/Waste/LitterPollution/FileDownload.d.38314.en.pdf>
8. Tomar, M., and Borad, N., 2012, Use of AHP Method in Efficiency Analysis of Existing Water Treatment Plants, Int. J. of Engrg. Research and Dev., 1(7), 42-51